

**THE VOICES OF UNCERTAINTY TOWARDS VICTORY ECHOED
FROM THE HEART OF THE NON-PHYSICAL EDUCATION
MAJOR TEACHERS TEACHING FOLK DANCE**

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The Voices of Uncertainty Towards Victory Echoed from the Heart of the Non-Physical Education Major Teachers Teaching Folk Dance

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Abstract

This study uncovered the lived experiences of the non-physical education major teachers teaching folk dance. In the literature, many studies focus on the misalignment of what the teachers finished and what they are teaching however, none of these studies center on the non-physical education major teachers. With this gap, teachers settle on letting the learners watch videos as a substitute. This study used interpretative phenomenology as the research design. The 15 participants volunteered and were chosen through purposive sampling, ensuring that only those currently teaching Folk dance with a degree are not inclined to Physical Education. Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) was used to analyze the data gathered through interviews and Focus Group discussions (FGD). There are three (3) core themes generated, namely, (1) The RELIC, (2) The RENAISSANCE, and (3) The REAL HAPPINESS IN TEACHING. These three core themes depict a picture of the situation and status quo of those teachers teaching Folk Dance or any topics under Physical Education where their college degree was not inclined to Physical Education. These teachers are struggling but thriving; although they may accept whatever subject they will teach, they know that if what they are teaching is their cup of tea, they will surely provide the promise of quality education. This study recommends strong implementation of vertical articulation and more exposure to the teachers in terms of improving their craft where they excel.

Keywords: *non-physical education teachers, pedagogy, phenomenology, folk dance, vertical articulation*

Introduction

Teachers are committed to upholding what is written in the Philippine Constitution, and that is to provide quality education to all learners. It is the primary responsibility of a teacher to share the most reliable knowledge and information with the class. In the educational context in the Philippines, some teachers are teaching, not their field of expertise (Abella & De Jesus, 2021). Due to the lack of teachers, especially those in the hinterland areas, 80% of the teachers are assigned to teach different subjects. This is what they called misalignment of the subject area. There are existing pieces of literature regarding this gap (Galang, 2021; Tapales, 2024). However, no study has yet focused on the teacher's lived experiences in teaching Folk Dance while their major is not Physical Education (PE). Teaching Folk Dance in High School is not an easy task if your line of expertise is not in PE and dance (Limanskaya et al., 2020). This study explicated the lived experiences of those non-PE major teachers whose voices of uncertainty are not heard with their current unique challenges of having Physical Education classes so that the current gap can be addressed by sound recommendations that the Department of Education can take cognizance of.

When the School Principal assigns a teacher to teach, not their field of expertise, teachers have no choice but to accept the challenge. Along with this comes several difficulties in delivering quality instructions (Hobbs & Porsch, 2021). Teachers who are not experts in what they are doing may feel anxious, which increases their level of stress, and their self-confidence drops as they face their students (Arendain & Limpot, 2022). They will feel as if they are not a page ahead of their students. Insecurity comes in, and teachers need to handle this every time they have their class. The action of executing dance figures and steps and the content or the expected knowledge that students should learn is full of uncertainty. This questions what is stipulated in the Philippine Constitution wherein every learner deserves a quality education that comes with competent and reliable teachers in teaching the essential competencies.

The teacher's feeling of insecurity is valid. Since the teacher is not a PE major, the scarcity of theoretical and practical knowledge and foundation in dance, anatomy, movement, proper execution, and the strategy, method, and technique of teaching may bring about compromising learning competencies (Bugwak, 2021). This can lead to a ripple effect on the learner's learning pool of knowledge (Racede et al., 2023). Teachers will rely on textbooks, audio-visual instructional materials, and online videos as supplementary teaching tools to address the teacher's lack of training and exposure to the subject matter (Apau, 2022). Teaching Folk Dance is not easy. It requires different classroom management strategies in which the teacher should consider the space inside the classroom, the technique of motivating learners to participate, and how to let them feel the importance of why Folk Dance should be danced as a way to appreciate Filipino culture (Bontigao et al., 2022).

There are existing pieces of literature showing how teachers extend their best in teaching a subject matter, not in their line of expertise. According to Cabello et al. (2022), when teachers experience extreme adjustment inside the classroom, they should constantly check their Psychological Well-Being and their self-consciousness. Doing this can help them survive on a day-to-day basis. This is supported by Montero et al. (2022), who focused more on the experiences of English Major teachers teaching MAPEH in Junior High School, wherein the results generated themes that can describe how the experiences of the participants need to do self-study regarding the content of the subject matter. Aside from this, they need to grow in resilience despite the odds. They have to face and conquer unique

challenges and difficulties especially when the teacher is not into performing activities.

Teaching Folk dance can be enriching as teachers allow learners to appreciate the rich culture of the country by reminiscing the essence of the dance and executing its steps and figures (Reyes et al., 2020; Lobo, 2022). When this subject is taught by a non-PE major teacher, this will not be appreciated as there will be varying levels of problems that both teacher and learners will experience (Arciosa et al., 2023; No & Esguerra, 2023). The different personal experiences of the non-PE major teacher can be a motivating factor that School Principals should take into account. This study unravels the voices, situations, and learning curves of non-PE major teachers in teaching Folk dance. Their learning experiences can be a source of how other teachers teaching not their field can survive and somehow, thrive in the teaching profession. Through the recommendations of this study, the upper management in the Department of Education can craft an essential action plan to address this most pressing issue happening in every school, if not now, in a particular division.

Research Questions

This study explored the lived experiences of non-PE major teachers teaching folk dance in High School in the Philippines. Specifically, this study answers the following questions:

1. What are the lived experiences of the non-PE major teachers?
2. What are the varying levels of unique challenges and problems they encounter in their class?
3. What are their learning opportunities and possible discoveries of pedagogy in handling a folk dance class?
4. What are their coping strategies in facing the different challenges they encountered in their class?
5. What is the essence of their experiences and how can this be used to listen to their unheard voices of uncertainty echoed from their heart?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used the Heideggerian Phenomenology as the research design. This research design digs deeper into understanding the lived experiences of the participants to a particular phenomenon. This inquiry investigated the lived experiences of non-PE major teachers teaching folk dance in High School in the Philippines.

Participants

This study verifies and checks all those non-PE major teachers teaching folk dance in High School in the Philippines. 40 teachers volunteered to participate in the interview. The data saturation was reached in the 15th participant. All the answers were recorded through the mobile phone of the researcher. A Focus Group Discussion (FGD) was also conducted to enrich the answers of the participants. The FGD lasted for 40 minutes. All answers of the participants were also recorded upon the request of the researcher agreed by the participants.

Instruments

In a qualitative inquiry, the main instrument is the researcher. In this study, along with the researcher, are the validated semi-structured interview guide questions. These questions were checked and validated by the experts. The semi-structured interview guide questions are dependent on the kind of participants that the researcher will be interviewing. The researcher can also ask follow-up questions when necessary.

Procedure

The first step that the researcher considered is to create a letter to request to gather data. After the letter was approved by the proper authorities, the researcher arranged for a schedule among the participants. The researcher must have a schedule as this might disrupt the classes. The researcher maximized the mobile phone and social media such as Messenger in Facebook to communicate with the participants. Once approved by the participants, the researcher initiated the interview, and before the interview, the researcher secured the consent and explained well the ethics of the research. For the Focus Group Discussion (FGD), the researcher had it online due to the geographical locations of the participants. After the interview and the FDG, the researcher managed to record the answers of the participants. This data will then be analyzed using the analysis that the researcher of this study decided to utilize.

Data Analysis

The study utilized the Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) popularized by Moustakas and modified by Van Kaam. The following are the steps in analyzing the data and how the meaning of the lived experiences of the participants is determined. These are the steps in analyzing the data. The following steps are horizontalization, Reduction, and elimination, Thematizing the Invariant Constituents, Checking the Themes Against the Data, Creating the Individual Textural Descriptions, Creating Individual Structural Descriptions, Creating Composite Textural Descriptions, Making the Composite Structural Descriptions, and the Creation of the Composite Structural-Textural Description.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher observed ethical principles throughout the conduct of the study. The researcher acknowledged the protection of privacy, anonymity, and dignity of respondents involved in the study as it is of paramount importance. The researcher also ensured that the gathered data from the participants were given with the highest degree of confidentiality. The participants were neither harmed nor coerced throughout the study.

Results and Discussion

After the analysis, the three emerging themes were elicited and proved to provide a clear picture of the lived experiences of non-PE major teachers teaching Folk Dance. The three (3) core themes generated are, namely, (1) The RELIC, (2) The RENAISSANCE, and (3) The REAL HAPPINESS IN TEACHING. These themes are discussed and elaborated below.

The RELIC

The first theme, the RELIC, is an abbreviation of Risk of Injury, Embarrassment, Lack of Exposure, Inconsistent Instruction, and Compromised Competencies in Folk Dance. Aside from this abbreviation, it is important to also understand the meaning of the word as it describes the length of time staying in the Philippine Educational Realm. A relic is a historical object that survived through time. This is the same with the teachers who survived through the test of time. A Non-PE major teacher is a relic with unique challenges. This description and the relic abbreviation, which are also the subthemes of this theme, are strengthened through the different lived experiences of the participants stipulated below.

Participant 2 said that,

There are times jud nga makulbaan ko matapilok kay pag motudlo bya kag sayaw kay imoha jud ng e perform nya dili pa kaayo ko mayo jud. Mao nang duol kau sya sa injury. Honestly, nasugsug nako ug bamboo sa pagdemo ug sayaw sa folk dance. Kuyaw jud sya kung dili ka kabalo sa dance kaayo pero wala koy choice kay gihatag man sa akua sa principal kay walay lain makahandle (P2).

“There are times when I get nervous and have a bad jump because when you teach the dance, you have to perform it, and the sad thing is I’m not very good at it. That’s when he was close to injury. Honestly, I learned bamboo to demo and dance folk dance. It’s dangerous if you don’t know how to dance, but I have no choice because the principal gave it to me. After all, no one else can handle it.”

Participant 1 mentioned that,

The moment you are in front of your students, you are expected to deliver the right information. The concepts can be discussed, though, but when you perform the folk dance, it is very difficult, and I am out of the timing. It was a very embarrassing moment when I just let them watch videos on YouTube for them to have a visual because I could not do it. I felt bad about myself, but I had to handle class because no one would.

Participants 5 and 7 added,

Teaching Folk dance is not really easy at all. Kailangan alam mo hindi lang sa knowledge o content na e dedeliver mo but how to execute the basic steps. In my case, I get to prepare every day what to share to them. Sometimes, I dedicate my time at home practicing the dance steps (P5).

“Teaching folk dance is not really easy at all. You need to know not only the knowledge or content you deliver but how to execute the basic steps. In my case, I get to prepare every day what to share with them. Sometimes, I dedicate my time at home practicing the dance steps (P5).”

Basically, we lack resources and support when we teach folk dance. Our principal is aware of it. Hindi namin kaya na kami lang kaso wala kaming choice kaya na kokompromise yung delivery of instruction. Nawawala yung confidence ko pag hindi ko alama ang gawin. Kaya I just resort to group them and let them discover things. Kung ano yung mabibigay nila, yun na yun (P7).

“We lack resources and support when we teach folk dance. Our principal is aware of it. We can’t do it on our own because we have no choice so we will compromise the delivery of instruction. I lose my confidence when I don’t know what to do. So I just resort to grouping them and letting them discover things. Whatever they can give, that’s it (P7).”

Participant 3 elaborated that,

Teaching not your major is an add-on burden. The upper management should look into this case as this is already happening not just to our school but across all schools in the district and even in the entire division. I need to prepare and preparing it is more demanding than teaching it because I don’t know at all how to dance. I was not exposed before because this is not just for me. And yet, I am teaching it because no one will in our school. There are just 4 of us here since it is a far-flung school. We have a limited number of teachers and classrooms. The instructions are not clear because I am confused sometimes. Inconsistency is obvious in discussing topics in Physical Education. I am assigned to teach PE and yet my major is Filipino. I am tired. I am exhausted. But I can’t resign because of my loans. And it has been a while since I have been in this situation. I hope I will be transferred to the coastal area so I will have the

chance to teach my field (P3).

Participant 9 discussed that,

I don't think I am effective in teaching Folk Dance. Although I am trying, I still know that my students are having problems appreciating the subject. I can't force them to be engaged in the subject matter. I think in today's time, school principals should know how to align the teacher's degree to what they should be teaching as this can impact the teacher's self-confidence and self-esteem, the delivery of the lesson, the students, and even the comments of the community. Teachers are to be blamed all the time when their children cannot perform well in the competencies. I blame myself for not doing it right, yet I need to blame the management for not allowing me to teach what I want to teach. I hope this cycle of poor management can be addressed as it has a ripple effect on the learners. I am not productive. The essential competencies are compromised (P9).

The RELIC is a theme that can summarize all the negative experiences that teachers encountered when teaching Folk dance, even if they are not Physical Education majors. This theme can give a clear picture of what the school principal should do in solving non-alignment issues. This problem should be elevated to the Department of Education (DepEd) so that appropriate actions can be initiated. If this problem is resolved, the promise of quality education is ensured to be given to the learners especially those who are enthusiastically inclined to dance cultural and folk dances.

The RENAISSANCE

The second theme, RENAISSANCE, also means REBIRTH. This means the moment of seeing the light after the era of darkness. This is where the process of learning, the baptism of fire in learning, and the learning curves are happening. The learning path of knowing what to learn, how to learn, what to relearn, and what to unlearn is happening at this time. REBIRTH is also an abbreviation of the identified subthemes under this theme, which are Rekindling New Ideas, Executing The Process, Best Learning Curve in Life, Instructional Preparation, Realizing the Essence of Positive Engagement, Thinking of What to Offer, and the Heart of Accepting the Challenge. The meaning of this theme and its subthemes are well supported by the claims and discussions of the participants which are indicated below.

Participant 4 expressed that,

Acceptance is the key kay thankful nata nga makatudlo oi. I know moreklamo ang uban pero lantawon nimo ang nag wait sa item, daghan kaayo. So, given the chance that I can teach maskin unsa pana, akoa jung dawaton. 5 years nako kapin nagteach ug PE which apil na ana ang Folk Dance and okay raman sya. Kapoy usahay pero makaya raman. Wala man poy work nga ayahay. Ma enjoy rajud ko kanang naa puy di kabalo mosayaw kay parehas mi pero naningkamot jud ug maayo. Parehas raming tanan learners sa classroom and it makes sense kay kung maayo napod kaayo kas subject matter, di napod ka pa correct. Maayo ng tanan nag learn together. This is a way on discovering new ways and new things (P4).

Acceptance is the key because we are thankful to be able to teach. I know others will complain, but look at the people who are waiting for the item, there are too many of them. So, given the chance that I can teach anything, I will accept it. I have been teaching PE for more than 5 years which includes Folk Dance and it is fine. It's tiring sometimes but it's manageable. There is no easy work. I will always enjoy the ones who don't know how to dance because we are the same but we are trying hard. We are all the same learners in the classroom and it makes sense because if you know the subject matter very well, you don't like to be corrected. It's good that everyone learns together. This is a way of discovering new ways and new things (P4).

Participant 5 said that,

When the steps in Folk Dance are just being danced and executed, you will be able to master it. We, teachers, are jack of all trades. We need to master it even if it is not our field of expertise. With constant practice, we will be able to nail it (P5).

Participant 7 added,

Bilang isang guro, hindi pwede na walang challenges. Ang pagtuturo ng Folk dance ay talagang napakahirap lalo na ang nakuha kong PE subjects ay apat lang sa college. Pero nakaya kong magturo sa mahigit na 6 na taon. Unti-unting napamahal ko ang pagtuturo sa asignaturang ito. This helped me to stay fit kasi I am always dancing. I am also joining different dance workshop. Accepting this challenge 6 years ago is indeed a blessing in disguise. I love embracing our culture. I love executing the dance steps showing the true color and identity of being a Pinoy. This is for me the learning curve where I get to learn a lot (7).

As a teacher, you can't be a teacher without challenges. Teaching Folk dance is very difficult, especially since I only got 4 PE subjects in college. But I was able to teach for more than 6 years. Gradually, I fell in love with teaching this subject. This helped me to stay fit because I am always dancing. I am also joining different dance workshops. Accepting this challenge 6 years ago is indeed a blessing in disguise. I love embracing our culture. I love executing the dance steps, showing the true color and identity of being a Pinoy. This is, for me, the learning curve where I get to learn a lot (7).

Participant 10 said that,

The most important thing po sigyro ay yung preparation. Kung prepared po tayong mga guro, hindi po mahirap ituro ang isang subject.

In our school po, we are supported by our administration in terms of preparing relevant instructional materials po. In teaching Folk dances, I usually request the materials ahead po time po kasi ayoko na ang mga students ang mag prepare ng mga kagamitan sap ag sasayaw. During naman sa aming culmination activity, I asked them during the first day of the school year to prepare the costume for presentation. For me, enough preparation can bring out the best teaching and learning experiences inside the classroom (P10).

The most important thing is probably the preparation. If we teachers are prepared, it is not difficult to teach a subject. In our school, we are supported by our administration in terms of preparing relevant instructional materials. In teaching Folk dances, I usually request the materials ahead of time because I don't want the students to prepare the equipment for dancing. During our culmination activity, I asked them during the first day of the school year to prepare the costumes for the presentation. For me, enough preparation can bring out the best teaching and learning experiences inside the classroom (P10).

Participant 6 mentioned that,

I know that Physical Education is not my major, but it is not a good reason not to have a classroom conducive to learning where everyone is positively engaged in the discussion or demonstration. I usually used the model technique in teaching folk dance. I dance first, then they follow. This has been my technique for quite some time. This makes me happy to go to work and teach my learners (P6).

Participant 8 narrated that,

Transition is just normal in teaching. Every year I get to have new subjects but teaching PE is really consistent. Since 2017, I have been a PE teacher and now I am the one making the supplementary activities in our school. I am the assigned key person for our PE days and whatever seminars and training workshops invitations our school receives, I will be the one to take charge of even if my major is Math in college. We don't have teachers whose major is MAPEH. So, no one has a brave soul to accept the challenge of accepting this subject but just me. With constant prayer and faith in God Almighty, I am surviving every day. I am thriving. I will continue to do my best to serve my students as their steward in providing the best learning experience they can get from me. I will always think of what to give and offer to my class (P8).

Participant 14 shared that,

There are different reactions I had when my school principal assigned me to teach PE. I am not that energetic to teach the subject. I am more on cooking. My major is Technology and Livelihood Education. What I know and what I want to share is all about what I learned from college. Reality hits me pag dawatako sa akong mga subjects. Honestly, nag think jud ko nga basin dili ganahan akong principal sa akong. Kabalo sya nga hilumon ko, hinayon ug ganahan ra nga dili tagdon, gitagaan jud kog subject nga need nako moadto usahay sa stage labi na kanang mag practice practice ug folk dance. I can't see myself doing it pero akong gidawat. Until now naa japon koy PE pero arang arang na kay duha nalang. Gi tunga tunga na ang ubang PE subjects. Pwd ni sya nga advantage pero pwede pod nga dili sya advantage kay daghan ug preparations. I hope makahimo ug move ani among division nga tagaan mig PE major jud nya sya tanan para one prep ra nya iyaha jud nga field. But I am happy to accept this task such as teaching Folk dance as this is still all about teaching and preserving our culture (P14).

There are different reactions I had when my school principal assigned me to teach PE. I am not that energetic to teach the subject. I am more into cooking. My major is Technology and Livelihood Education. What I know and what I want to share is all about what I learned from college. Reality hits me when I receive my subjects. Honestly, I thought maybe my principal didn't like me. He didn't know how to talk to me, he said it and he just ignored me at all. I can't see myself doing it but I just accepted it. Until now, I have PE subjects, but it's only for two classes. The other PE subjects are distributed halfway. It may be an advantage but it may not be an advantage because of many preparations. I hope our division can make a move to give us a PE major so that he can only have one prep field. But I am happy to accept this task such as teaching Folk dance as this is still all about teaching and preserving our culture (P14).

The second theme, RENAISSANCE, is not only giving birth to new knowledge and ideas but also appreciating the light it served to accept and live the life of being a teacher. Everyone has a learning curve to face in life and it is essential to learn from the different encounters along the way. It is not the destination that matters most because others end their race without reaching the destination, it is the learning experiences or the journey that matters. Being a teacher is living a life full of challenges and breakthroughs, especially inside the classroom. It is important to remember that in every challenge teachers encounter, there is a better opportunity and room to grow.

The REAL HAPPINESS IN TEACHING

The third theme, The REAL HAPPINESS IN TEACHING, exemplifies the accomplishment and fulfillment of the teachers, especially when they are in situations of severe challenges and able to achieve breakthroughs in teaching. The subthemes under this third theme are abbreviated as REAL, which stands for Resounding Applause, Excitement and Enthusiasm, Amazing Profession, and the Love of Teaching. These subthemes are the results of coming from scratch, such as learning new ideas and techniques in folk dance and knowing how to teach the concepts and movements to the students. Seeing the students learn the proper steps and movements of folk dance can be a milestone among non-PE major teachers. They will think about how much more if their major is Physical Education. This is an added value to how versatile and resilient a teacher can be. These themes and statements are aggrandized by the experiences of the

participants indicated below.

Participant 15 said,

I think it is just a process of accepting things. Mayroon naman nagtuturo na English even if they finished MAPEH and I think it's just normal for us teachers to be bombarded with challenges. Dito kami naging magaling. Dito kami tinaguriang the Maker of all Professions o yung kami ang gumagawa sa ibang professions kasi kami yung nag seset ng foundation of learning eh. Kaya I believe na we should be flexible and we have to embrace the process of learning new things every single day. That is we deserve an applause and tap on our back for choosing this career (P15).

I think it is just a process of accepting things. There are those who teach English even if they finished MAPEH and I think it's just normal for us teachers to be bombarded with challenges. This is where we excelled. Here we are called the Maker of all Professions or we are the ones who make other professions because we are the ones who set the foundation of learning. So I believe that we should be flexible and we have to embrace the process of learning new things every single day. That is we deserve applause and tap on our back for choosing this career (P15).

Participant 11 added,

Learning is a lifelong process indeed. I love that I am learning new things every time I handle my PE class. Teaching Folk Dance is not all about the proper execution. We are not all dancers. This is the same with our learners. Dili silang tanan kabalo pod mosayaw. Ang importante ani kay matudlo and concepts, mapakita ang steps, and ma appreciate sa mga learners ang atong kultura. My major way back sa college kay history maong duol duol ra except sa sayawon jud kung mahimo ang mga steps sa pagtudlo sa folk dance. And I am learning it. I am loving it. And evertime mosulod ko, ma excite jud ko. I can feel nga ma excite pod akong mga students pag mosulod ko sa class. Because of this, kaluy an sa Ginoo, 8 years nako nag teach ug PE labi na ang Folk Dance. I would somehow recommend nga ihatag sya sa major jud sa PE ng teacher pero okay nako. Ganahan rako. I think effective rapod ko kay nindot man ang output sa akong mga students. I am always excited to teach and share what I know on how to dance especially showing our culture (P11).

Learning is a lifelong process indeed. I love that I am learning new things every time I handle my PE class. Teaching Folk Dance is not all about the proper execution. We are not all dancers. This is the same with our students. Not all of them know how to dance. The important thing is to teach concepts, show the steps, and make the learners appreciate our culture. My major way back in college was history, so it is quite related except for dancing if the steps in teaching folk dance could be done. And I am learning it. I love it. And every time I go in, I get excited. I can feel the students get excited when I enter the class. Because of this, thanks to the Lord, I taught PE, especially Folk Dance, for 8 years. I would somehow recommend giving it to the teacher's PE major, but I'm okay with it. I like teaching this subject. I think I am effective because the output from my students is good. I am always excited to teach and share what I know about how to dance, especially showing our culture (P11).

Participant 13 said that,

Teaching Folk Dance is not that easy since this is not my major. But I get to learn how to do it. I get to go beyond what is being expected to teach. I know how to dance since I was a hip-hop dancer before, but it is different when folk dance is being taught and executed in a PE class. But this is the nature of being a teacher. We get to understand the concept and try our best to teach it. I just hope that the principal can help other teachers who are not teaching their field because it's different. It can be learned, but it is different, especially when you think that there is more that you can share, such as techniques on how to dance it, your experiences of doing it, and the concepts and knowledge shared by your instructors in college and be able to cascade it to your learners. Teaching is truly an amazing profession (P13).

Participant 12 discussed that,

I love that I am embracing the teaching of Folk Dance, especially Subli. I love how the girls would show grace and elegance in dancing this. Truly, I can mirror this to how our women of before act and live. I like that we bring to life the cultural heritage of our country. The essence of preserving the culture is somehow what I think I can contribute significantly to our dear country. I may encounter challenging tasks in teaching this, but I have all the resources I need. I have the technological tools that can augment and address the gap I am encountering daily. My major is English, and yet I am teaching aside from English, Filipino, and PE. I am happy teaching these subjects. For me, this is a blessing, and I want to treasure this for the rest of my life. Aside from this is what sustains me, teaching is my life (P12). The last theme emphasized the importance of being a mature and professional person, embracing the different strokes in life, especially in teaching. The different challenges are just the starters that can give spice to how one survives and thrives in the world of teaching. Learning the concept is easy, and executing the concepts in Physical Education may be challenging, but when a teacher's heart is in place and ready to accept whatever it is that will come across, everything will follow smoothly. The most important is to understand the nature of one's profession and live with it.

Conclusion

While it is true that non-PE teachers are having difficulties adjusting because of vertical misalignment, they were still able to champion

above all circumstances. This study proved that Filipino teachers are versatile and resilient, especially showing how they can handle the teaching of Folk Dance. They may use different tools to augment the scarcity in classroom instruction but are still able to manage to deal with all distractions and limited resources. The participants showed that they are RELIC who can survive because they undergo the RENAISSANCE period of learning and teaching, which makes them fulfilled teachers discovering the REAL HAPPINESS OF TEACHING. This can be a reference to how teachers consider themselves the most flexible profession and even the makers of other professions. When they are given a task to do, they will exhaust everything to perform more than what is expected of them. It is recommended that the upper management of the Department of Education (DepEd) take action on this issue of misalignment. It can be a short-term or a long-term goal. The school head can initiate the short-term goal by balancing the load of the teachers. If a lack of teachers is the problem, then teachers can share the PE loads with a subject leader. In this way, it will not be so heavy for the teachers to handle loads in Physical Education subject. It can also be decided if there will be one teacher who will handle all the PE subjects yet, if that teacher is not a PE major, that teacher should be sent to all training and seminars in Physical Education, which can be a supplementary exposure to the teacher. For the long-term goal, the DepEd should manage to hire the ones with the proper degree program vertically and horizontally aligned to the lacking teachers in each school. DepEd can also initiate monitoring of the teachers' profiles to make sure that this issue of misalignment will be dealt with.

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